

Church of St. George, Embaros

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Entry tags: Crete, Religious Group, Byzantine, Church, Byzantine, Religious Place, Medieval Christianity, Orthodoxy, Monument

Located in the center of the village of Embaros in the Padiada Eparchy, the church of St. George in Embaros is a single nave construction with a pointed barrel vault. Divided into three bays, the raised transverse arches are decorated at each of their terminuses with a coat of arms on a red ground, presumably that of the donor's family. The exterior is composed of exposed stone covered by a tiled gable roof. The primary entrance, located on the west side of the building, is framed by a pointed arch which once likely held a painting, now whitewashed. The roof is topped by a later belfry. A modern window has been inserted into the center of the north wall. The village of Embaros, at the base of the Dikti Mountains, is one of the largest villages in the area with records of the village dating back to the early fourteenth century. Located in the valley of the Mparitis River, the region is lush with agricultural products from olive oil to wine production. Although agriculture is the primary occupation of the community, they are also well known for their ditany, or mountain tea. The church of St. George, with its well-preserved frescoes, was commissioned by, according to the dedicatory inscription preserved on the west wall above an image of the archangel Michael, the contribution and efforts of the priest Manuel, his wife and children, along with several other Christians, during the reign of the emperor John VIII Palaiologos (r. 1425-48) in the year 6945 (1436-1437) and painted by the hand of Manuel Phokas. Although the wall paintings are damaged, they are of a high quality, reflecting the art of the major artistic centers of the Byzantine world. The sanctuary is, today, separated by a modern wooden iconostasis built into the wall just beyond the easternmost transverse arch. Heavily damaged, the sanctuary wall paintings reveal only remnants of the figure of Christ Pantocrator in the apse, the Hospitality of Abraham in the upper part of the triumphal arch, and deacons and co-officiating bishops along the lower register. The sanctuary barrel vault is in better condition showing the scenes of the Pentecost and the Ascension. The apostles appear amidst ornate contemporary buildings and mountainous landscapes. Below these scenes, two additional scenes, the Incredulity of Thomas, on the south, and Christ Appearing to the Two Marys, on the north, are flanked to the west by an unidentifiable martyr (on the north) and an ornate floral pattern (on the south). The nave, divided into two by a transverse arch decorated with busts of saints, includes three registers of narrative scenes from the Christological cycle and the Life and Martyrdom of St. George. The height of the church and the quality of the painting allows each scene to be rendered in fine detail with the figures positioned amidst dramatic land and cityscapes. The life of St. George includes six scenes from the life and martyrdom of the saint with the unusually combined scene of St. George in the Lime Pit and St. George in the Furnace. The lower register on both the north and south walls displays rows of saints framed under a red archway decorated with floral motifs. The northern wall includes the images of three female saints next to two medical saints, Sts. Cosmas and Damian, identified by their boxes of medicinal powders and ladles. Along the southern wall, unobstructed by the modern window are a similar row of standing saints, albeit badly preserved. Among these only the images of the Saints Constantine and Helena can be readily identified. The western wall, heavily damaged, shows the Last Judgment with the outer figures from the Apostles Tribunal and the Angels Rolling up the Heavens visible on either side of the scene. To the left of the entrance the image of the Archangel Michael is framed below the dedicatory inscription. The scene of the Pool of Fire along with a few figures of the damned, albeit very damaged, is visible on the right side of the entrance.

Date Range: 1436 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Village of Embaros, Pediada, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The village of Embaros, at the base of the Dikti Mountains, is one of the largest villages in the area with records of the village dating back to the early fourteenth century.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: Located in the center of the village.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

- Other [specify]: Other: Single nave chapel with a pointed vault interior and a saddle roof exterior.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. George

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

–Trackway or road-surface

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The church is located at the center of the village of Embaros.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

–Other [specify]: According to the dedicatory inscription, the church was built by the contribution and efforts of the priest Manuel, his wife and children, along with several other Christians in the community.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

–Other [specify]: Located in the center of the village.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

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- No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Other: Single nave chapel with a pointed vault interior and a saddle roof exterior.

- ↳ One single feature
 - Clearing

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. George

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Extensive wall paintings.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There is a modern wooden iconostasis separating the sanctuary

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include images of Christ in the Christological cycle.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include standing figures of saints, monks and prophets. it also includes scenes from the life of the titular saint, St. George.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include images of individual sinners along with people associated with the life of Christ and the Life of St. George

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icon paintings are incorporated into the iconostasis.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The painting cycle reflects standard iconography of the Orthodox Christian faith

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the dedicatory inscription, there are inscriptions identifying the figures (including both the saints and the individual sinners). there are also titles on many of the

narrative scenes.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: There is a formal dedicatory inscription on the west wall of the church above the image of the Archangel Michael

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Includes scenes from both the Christological Cycle and the Life of St. George.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, brick, stone

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

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↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

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Iconography

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↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives
– Yes

Notes: Includes scenes from both the Christological Cycle and the Life of St. George.

↳ Human narratives
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
–specify: unknown

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: unknown

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

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– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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